

IMPROVEMENT OF LITERARY COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN HIGHER SCHOOL

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Abstract. *In the sphere of modern education, special attention is paid to research works on improving the methodology of development of literary competences, formation on the basis of integrative approach of professional competence of students studying in the direction of education "Literary Studies", as well as improving their knowledge and skills. In this article the author faces the task of identifying pedagogical opportunities in the development of literary competences of future teachers, as well as the development of an algorithm of aesthetic properties of the word on an interdisciplinary-integrative basis in the development of literary competences in the analysis and interpretation of the artistic text.*

Keywords: *literature, literary competences, literary studies, artistic work, text interpretation, activity*

Introduction.

In higher educational institutions of the world, innovative technologies of developing literary competences of future teachers are being introduced into the educational process. In higher educational institutions of the USA, Russia, Canada, England, Great Britain, Korea, Columbia, China, systematic works on theoretical bases of formation of literary competences, as well as formation of literary and speech competences, communicative approach in the study of literary studies, development of analysis of art works with the help of pedagogical technologies are carried out. In recent years, our republic has been creating normative foundations for the training of professionally competent, highly qualified teachers capable of ensuring the quality of education in higher educational institutions, based on national and advanced foreign experience, as well as the development of literary competences of future teachers. The priority task was defined as "..... in-depth study of other important and demanded subjects such as literature, improving the quality and efficiency of higher education institutions based on the implementation of international standards for assessing the quality of education and teaching" . As a result, the opportunities for conducting scientific research on the development of literary competencies of future teachers have expanded. This research was carried out in accordance with the priority direction of science and technology development of the Republic "Formation of the system of innovative ideas and ways of their realization in social, legal, economic, cultural, spiritual and educational development of information society and democratic state".

Literature review

Questions of speech development and independent thinking, formation of analytical skills of teachers, organization of creative works in the system of literary education are investigated by A.Zunnunov, S.Matchanov, K.Yuldashev, B.Tukhliyev, M.Mirkasymova, G.Khusanbaeva, R.Niyazmetova, B.Kadyrov, F.Egamberdiyeva. Egamberdiyeva; linguistic peculiarities of art works at the stages of education, study in interrelation with educational disciplines "Mother tongue" and "Literature" by K.Yadgarov, A.Aliyev, K.Abdullayev, B.Fozilova, K.Mavlonova;

methodology of development of literary-speech and language competences in language education by O.Kurbanova, M.Kenjaeva.

In CIS countries: in the research works of such scientists as E. Minkina, R. Doshinsky, O.B. Sirotnina, N.F. Titova, Y. Ganshina, E. Markina, G. Mamon, A. Loichenko, A. Alferova, I. Apalkova, N. Semenova, N. Nikitin, R. Ramazanov the ways of work are covered. Ramazanov highlighted the ways of working on the style and linguistic features of the artistic text, the development of literary speech, integrated teaching of the academic disciplines "Native Language" and "Literature".

Main body

The issues of literary competences development in higher education institutions are becoming more and more important and urgent. Such renewal is largely facilitated by competence-oriented learning, which requires the creation of an educational environment capable of ensuring the formation of students' competencies in certain spheres of activity. Since literary studies is a science that leads the conversation about fiction, it is necessary to consistently study the general theoretical data about it in the following order. "Literature" (Latin lit(t)eratura, - written, from lit(t)era - letter) in practice is used both in a broad and narrow sense. In the broad sense, the scope of "literature" includes books, pamphlets, articles and, in principle, works written and published for mass reading (distributed in manuscript form in the period before the opening of the printing house).

The term "literature" (French: litterature-written literature) appeared in the world science in the XVIII-XIX centuries. This term actually arose as a result of the merger of the words letter and logos; literature means printed word, mainly used in the meaning of "written literature".

Also, in developing literary competences, it is mainly important to develop students' literary and speech competence (listening comprehension, oral expression of thought, reading, expression of thought in writing), as well as competence in analyzing a work of fiction - the ability to understand and retell the content of events described in the works recommended for independent reading, to react to the characters of the work, to learn through reading a fiction text not only grammar, but also through translation. In the course of the research work, the scientific works of several linguists and literary critics were analyzed extensively. Especially, if **N.M. Shansky[2]** declares that: "...under literary analysis of an artistic text is understood an analysis that synthesizes all the knowledge and achievements of linguistics, methodology, literary studies and cultural history", then the linguist **E. Kylychev[4]** in his book "Linguistic analysis of the text" gives the following definition: "Text is a complex structure representing nominative and aesthetic information, all elements of which are in close interrelation and directed, from the author's point of view, to a certain goal".

I. Rasulov[3], on the other hand, describes the text as follows: "A sentence is a complex syntactic whole consisting of a union of mentally and syntactically interconnected sentences. In it, a thought becomes more complete compared to a sentence".

Based on this, a fiction text can be divided into the following types: 1. A narrative-content text. 2. Illustrative text. 3. Explanatory-content text. 4. Didactic text. 5. Informative and informative text. 6. An imperative-content text. 7. Sensual-content text.

Analytical activity carried out in the process of considering the artistic text, as noted above, is aimed at interpreting the artistic text as its deep understanding. In this case, the artistic text is

considered as a constituent part of a literary and artistic work, which includes the rest of the extra-textual reality of the work.

According to the dictionary of terms of literary studies - interpretation (Latin interpretation - "interpretation, explanation") - 1) interpretation, disclosure of the meaning of something, explanation of this or that text; 2) creative performance of any artistic work on the basis of independent interpretation.

Interpretation in the broad sense is a way of studying an artistic work, limited to explaining the principles of content, style, artistic structure of the text.

The research work introduces clarifying characteristics of the definition of the concept of interpretation - it is a stage of generalization, synthesis, the final result of analysis, which is carried out in parallel with the analytical consideration of the text and is the highest level of its understanding.

The approaches described above allowed us to create a scheme of literary analysis and interpretation of an artistic text.

When developing literary competencies in future teachers, it is important to pay attention to the following features of teaching literature:

development of the mechanism of interdisciplinary integration in teaching literature;
creation of a scientific criterion for correct assessment of the level of mastering literature;
organization of methodical manuals, visual aids, multimedia and other didactic materials on teaching literature for future teachers;

development of ways to use the possibilities of information and communication technologies in stimulating teachers' interest in reading works of fiction.

Therefore, in the development of literary competences in future teachers, we paid attention to the aesthetic properties of the word and the process of their analysis in Russian and English. The following integrated tasks are defined in its content as aesthetic properties of literary terms and the basics of their analysis in Russian and English languages:

1. Ensuring that students master theoretical ideas about the main features of artistic speech, aesthetic features of the speech level of a literary work;
2. Identification of metaphorical and methodical means used in the text at all four: lexical, phraseological, grammatical, sound and rhythmic-intonational levels;
3. Highlighting the peculiarities of aesthetic word changes when comparing Uzbek, Russian and English languages;
4. Mastering lexical-semantic concepts in Russian and English languages (when interpreting fiction texts, special attention is paid to synonymy, antonymy, as well as homonymy of words, word combinations and syntactic constructions);
5. Study of paradigmatic concepts (the role of word groups in a fiction text) and syntagmatic concepts (the meaning of word order in a sentence, the design of a complete thought) in Russian and English;
6. Formation of students' skills to apply the acquired knowledge, independently organize and independently plan the analysis and interpretation of the aesthetic properties of the word;
7. Teaching a holistic artistic analysis and interpretation of the aesthetic properties of the word;
8. Enrichment of students' speech with figurative and expressive means.

Aesthetic properties of words and knowledge, skills and abilities obtained as a result of the process of their analysis in Russian and English languages allow students to increase their literary competence by mastering literary analysis and interpretation of a fiction text.

The developed model of development of literary competence of future teachers meets such basic didactic principles as: scientificity, systematicity, lucidity, joint application of various methods, means, forms of teaching, thoroughness. In this model, based on the goals and objectives of the research work on the development of literary competence of future teachers, as well as on the basis of feedback, the following should be noted:

1) the problem of speech-creative training development of literary competence of future teachers is solved at the present stage of education development on the basis of systemic, personal, activity, technological, social, communicative and other approaches.

2) the model is developed, which also includes the development of students' literary and speech competence by means of systemic, but characteristic for literary studies analysis and interpretation of the artistic text.

3) includes the peculiarities of aesthetic word changes in the comparison of Uzbek, Russian and English languages of the development of literary-speech competence.

The component of positive result of literary studies competence development through literary analysis and interpretation of the art text includes: control of learning outcomes, determination of the degree of formation of the studied competence and analysis of the final result.

The content-processual component of the process model of orientation to the development of literary competence of future teachers is characterized by special i.e. linguistic-educational, psychological and pedagogical blocks of training.

If we once again touch upon the organizational-technological component of the model of the process of developing communicative competence in future teachers, it is advisable that it should be represented by organizational forms that are innovative and reflect the communicative activities of the teacher and students.

The criterion-level component of the model includes a system of criteria to determine the level of development of the type of competence we study, i.e. high, medium, low levels (in particular, communicative-personal, didactic, and gnostic components).

Conclusion

The features of the developed model of the process of development of literary competence of future teachers are the analysis and interpretation of the artistic text, analysis of the aesthetic properties of the word.

So, aesthetic properties of the word and their analysis in Russian and English is an integrated learning process that allows to identify the most important features of analyzing fiction texts in Uzbek, Russian and English languages, to identify the features of bilingual conversation and its use, to analyze fiction speech at the vocabulary-phraseological, grammatical, sound and rhythmic-intonation levels and it is considered very important for pedagogical competence of future teachers.

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